

Deployment-Oriented Room-Level Wi-Fi Fingerprinting for Context-Aware Museum Wayfinding and Analytics

Winter Clinckemaillie*, Joachim Taelman*, Kenzo Milleville*, Steven Verstockt*

IDLab, Ghent University-imec, winter.clinckemaillie@ugent.be, joachim@taelman@ugent.be,
kenzo.milleville@ugent.be, steven.verstockt@ugent.be

Abstract

We present a Wi-Fi fingerprinting workflow for room-level localization in museums that supports context-aware content triggering and staff-facing wayfinding analytics. The approach increases robustness by selecting stable transmitters across devices/time and augmenting training to handle incomplete scans. In a museum deployment evaluated one year later, our best model achieves 94.4% room-level accuracy and remains effective under simulated missing transmitters.

Keywords: Wayfinding, Wi-Fi Fingerprinting, Indoor Localization

1. Introduction

Museums are multi-room environments where navigation challenges cause missed exhibits, detours, and visitor frustration. Indoor localization offers a dual advantage for cultural heritage institutions: it enables context-aware visitor experiences (e.g., triggering relevant content upon room entry) and provides staff with movement analytics to optimize signage and exhibition layout (Centorrino et al., 2021).

We focus on Wi-Fi Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) fingerprinting to leverage existing access points (APs) without dedicated infrastructure (Bahl & Padmanabhan 2000, Xia et al. 2017). However, practical deployments face several challenges, including temporal drift, varying transmitter visibility, device-dependent RSSI biases, and signal attenuation from layout changes or interference from museum artifacts (Khalajmehrabadi et al. 2017, Shang & Wang 2022, Li et al. 2024). Prior work has explored Wi-Fi localization specifically for museum environments (Bracco et al. 2020). Our work presents a deployment-oriented workflow to improve robustness by restricting inference to stable transmitters across devices and time, and by training models to handle incomplete scans.

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2. System Overview

The workflow consists of three phases (see *Figure 1*). Offline, staff collect labeled Wi-Fi scans at predefined reference points (RPs) using a floorplan-guided Android application. These fingerprints are then processed to train a light-weight classifier that maps signal features to RP labels, resulting in a versioned model package that includes the selected feature list. During visits, visitors use museum-provided tablets that scan for Wi-Fi hotspots every 5 seconds and run on-device inference. Location-based content is triggered upon room change detection. After the visit, the device uploads session logs. Server-side processing aggregates sessions into staff-facing indicators (heatmaps, trajectory flows, missed rooms).

Figure 1. Workflow overview: offline fingerprint collection and training, on-device inference and content triggering, and post-visit staff-facing analytics.

3. Case Study and Dataset

We evaluate in KOERS (Roeselare, Belgium), a museum spanning three floors and 15 rooms (total accessible area $\sim 3,100$ m²). We formulate localization as a discrete RP classification rather than coordinate regression to reduce calibration effort while still capturing within-room signal variation. We identified 52 RPs to represent spatial variation and transitions throughout the museum. *Figure 2* illustrates the discretization for one floor.

A fingerprint is a Wi-Fi scan containing observed Basic Service Set Identifiers (BSSIDs) with RSSI values. Each scan is converted into a fixed-length vector over a set of selected BSSIDs; missing entries are imputed with a noise-floor value (-100 dBm), consistent with common fingerprinting practices (Li et al. 2024).

Figure 2. Room discretization (one floor). Colored areas represent rooms (R1-R6) and are sampled by multiple reference points (blue-filled circles).

Table 1 summarizes the dataset. An auxiliary calibration set was acquired for stability-based feature selection (filtering unstable transmitters), while the test set (collected one year later) serves to evaluate temporal robustness under natural environmental changes.

Table 1. Overview of the dataset splits.

<i>Split</i>	<i>Collection time</i>	<i># Devices</i>	<i># Fingerprints</i>
<i>Train</i>	Initial collection (t_0)	4	2,127
<i>Calibration</i>	Follow-up ($t_0 + 1$ month)	1	270
<i>Test</i>	Long-term ($t_0 + 12$ months)	4	1,067

4. Localization Methodology

We evaluate edge-friendly classifiers: k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forests (RF), and Extra Trees (ET). We sum scores over all RPs in a room to predict the room label. Hyperparameters per method are tuned on training data using GroupKFold by device ID to mitigate device-dependent RSSI bias. Models are retrained on the full training split and evaluated on the one-year-later test split.

In operational settings, the set of visible transmitters varies due to transient devices (e.g., temporary hotspots) and network changes. This variability may also differ across devices. To reduce sensitivity to unstable transmitters and to lower input dimensionality, we apply a stability-based feature selection using training and calibration data. From 473 BSSIDs observed in

training (baseline feature space), we retain only those observed on all training devices and again in the one-month-later calibration round, yielding a final set of 221 stable BSSIDs.

Wi-Fi scans may be incomplete due to varying transmitter visibility and environmental factors, leading to missing features at inference time. To improve robustness, we apply data augmentation by creating one perturbed copy per sample by (i) randomly masking 30% of non-missing features to -100 dBm (feature dropout) and (ii) injecting Gaussian RSSI noise ($\sigma=4$ dB). This augmentation aims to reduce over-reliance on individual strong transmitters and to improve performance when parts of the feature set are unavailable. We report RP accuracy and room-level accuracy. To assess robustness against missing transmitters, we simulate AP dropout at test time by masking a random fraction of non-missing features and report performance at 0%, 30%, and 50% dropout.

5. Preliminary Results

Table 2 reports the RP and room-level accuracy on the one-year-later test split under three simulated dropout conditions. Across classifiers, the proposed configuration (stable BSSIDs and data augmentation) maintains performance at 0% dropout and improves robustness as dropout increases. Extra Trees (ET) performed best overall (94.4% room accuracy). Under 50% drop-out, ET room accuracy increases from 83.4% (baseline) to 89.7% (proposed), with a similar improvement in RP accuracy (64.1 to 69.2%). This indicates more graceful degradation when many transmitters are temporarily unavailable. The stability-based feature selection method halves the input dimensionality without compromising accuracy, validating its suitability for resource-constrained mobile devices.

Table 2. Reference point (RP) and room-level accuracy (percent) on the test split under simulated transmitter dropout (masking 0/30/50% of received RSSI features). Baseline: 473 BSSIDs, no augmentation. Proposed: 221 stable BSSIDs with data augmentation. Best per column in bold.

Model	Configuration	0% AP dropout		30% AP dropout		50% AP dropout	
		RP	Room	RP	Room	RP	Room
kNN	Baseline	72.6	93.8	57.6	85.3	15.7	40.1
	Proposed	76.6	93.1	63.4	90.1	27.8	58.4
SVM	Baseline	73.4	92.8	59.7	88.3	34.7	74.1
	Proposed	72.3	93.0	67.0	91.0	59.0	87.2
RF	Baseline	77.9	94.4	71.1	90.8	55.1	80.5
	Proposed	77.6	93.6	73.4	93.9	67.6	89.6
ET	Baseline	77.3	94.4	72.8	90.2	64.1	83.4
	Proposed	77.6	94.4	74.8	93.6	69.2	89.7

Aggregating room predictions across visits enables a room-level dwell-time heatmap (Figure 3) that summarizes visitor attention per room and highlights hotspots and under-visited areas.

Figure 3. Example room-level dwell-time heatmap aggregated across visits.

6. Conclusion

This study presents a deployment-oriented Wi-Fi fingerprinting workflow for room-level museum localization that is lightweight and robust to incomplete scans. Stability-based feature selection and training-time data augmentation improve robustness under severe simulated transmitter loss (ET: 89.7% room accuracy at 50% dropout) while keeping no-drop performance unchanged (94.4%). Future work will focus on improving trajectory fidelity by combining confidence-based thresholds with floorplan-graph constraints to suppress implausible transitions. Additionally, we aim to apply clustering to categorize visitor behavior and quantify the impact of layout changes on room dwell times.

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